

APPLICATION OF BLENDED LEARNING ON OPEN JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN INDONESIA

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Abstract: The purpose of this study is to investigate the implementation of blended learning in the Open Junior High School in Indonesia. This research is quantitative descriptive survey method. Primary data were obtained through questionnaires. The study sample consisted of students and teachers drawn from Cirebon regency. This research was conducted during June to December 2015. The results showed that: In planning the self-study, there were 16.7% of teachers said always to plan, 50% said often, 33% said sometimes, and none of the states rarely and never. In planning face to face, as much as 43.8% of teachers said always to plan, 50% said often, 6.3% said sometimes, and nothing that states rarely and never. But in planning online learning, as much as 12.5% of teachers said always to plan, 37.5% said often, 50% said sometimes, and nothing that states rarely and never. Implementation of blended learning in the Open Junior High School in Indonesia starting from the planning, implementation and evaluation of good.

Keywords: Blended Learning, Open Junior High School, Indonesia

INTRODUCTION

The demand for quality human resources able to compete in a global world, always calls for changes toward improving quality and competitiveness. The problem of education is to date that can not be solved and resolved is the extension and expansion of educational opportunities and improve the quality of education. In children aged 13-15 can not get an education because of constraints such as geographical barriers, socio-economic and demographic. To overcome this problem the government to develop an educational system called Open Junior High School.

Learning system in Junior High School Open learning systems on different premises Junior High School. In the Open Junior High School students give priority to learn independently with limited bantua of subject teachers with a teacher called Bina. The main learning material adalah print modules and supported by other learning media such as audio Casset, broadcast educasi TV, VCD and Video. To solve students' learning difficulties when the independent study, conducted learning through face-to-face (tutorial-face) Considering the age of junior secondary students Open is still relatively young, it is in the self-learning is often challenged, so the quality or learning outcomes students are less satisfactory or not in accordance to be expected. Thus, people often say the quality of junior high school graduates Open still low.

In order to improve the quality of the Open Junior High School, a wide variety of programs and efforts have been developed. Relates to methods and learning strategies has done much to improve the quality Open Junior High School in Indonesia. In order to improve learning outcomes and the quality of the learning process is in Junior High School Open Open. The process of combining strategies and methods developed through learning Blended learning strategies.

Blended learning concept is now more synonymous with an understanding of the integration of online self-study learning, independent learning with print modules, and learning face to face (face-to-face tutorials). Bonk and Graham (2006: 5) defines blended learning as "blended learning systems combine face-to-face instruction with computer-mediated instruction". According to Dabbagh and Bannan Ritland (2005: 15) says "online learning is an open and distributed learning environment that uses pedagogical tools, enabled by the Internet and web-based technologies, to Facilitate learning and knowledge building through meaningful action and interaction".

Bershin (2009) "Blended learning is the combination of different media training: technologies, activities, and types of events to create an optimal training program for a specific audience. Blended learning programs use many different forms of e-learning, perhaps complemented with instructor-led training and other live formats. While Driscoll & Carliner (2005: 234) defines: Blended learning integrates blends -or-learning programs in different formats to Achieve a common goal. Seaman, and Garrett (2007: 5) says that the definition of an online course or blended program is similar to the definition used for courses; an online program is one where at least 80 percent of the course content is delivered online and a blended program is one where between 30 and 79 percent of the course content is delivered online.

This is in line with that proposed by Betrus cited by Januszewski and Molenda (2008: 228-230), that the computer is now a major tool in making learning materials. The computer combines the functions of many tools and devices before, and deliver instruction in a safe and comfortable package for instructors and trainers. In addition, the functions are integrated, Internet-based computer has been generally replaced most of the tools and devices that preceded it. The types of learning materials are available for use with computers, among others including instructional videos, reference materials, audio recordings, and simulation learning. While many of these materials are available on CD or DVD, the current trend in accessing digital content made directly via the internet. According to the e-TQM College Blended learning Blended learning Approach (2009) is defined as follows: Blended learning is the combination of multiple approaches to learning. Blended learning can be accomplished through the use of 'blended' virtual and physical resources. A typical example of this would be a combination of technology-based materials and face-to-face sessions used together to deliver instruction. In the strictest sense, Blended learning is anytime any instructor combines two methods of delivery of instruction. Currently this area is divided into the following three sub areas.

Furthermore Wedemeyer in Keegan (1996: 59) gives the definition: Independent learning is that learning, that changed behavior, that results from activities Carried on by learners in space and time, learners Whose environment is different from that of the school, learners who may be guided by teachers but who are not dependent upon them, learners who accept degrees of freedom and responsibility in initiating and carrying out the activities that lead to learning. Implementation of blended learning using a variety of variations of the model. INACOL summarizes the continuum model used in schools across the country the United States to give educators working drawings of the many ways in which online learning integrates with and supports traditional instruction (face to face). Clearly blended learning models of INACOL can be shown in Figure 2.1. below this.

Figure 1. Continuum of Blended Learning Model

Here's an explanation of Figure 2.1. continuum of blended learning models. At first many schools may not start a blended learning approach by doing most of the instructions or online learning as a model 1 and model 2. In model 1 curriculum is fully carried out online with the option students may request instruction face-to-face, while the second model of the curriculum partly or completely conducted online with a few hours of study time either in the classroom or computer lab.

Furthermore Staker and Horn (2012: 8-15) grouping of four models of blended learning that a majority category blended learning program that appears in the K-12 sector today. The models are as follows: (1) rotation models, divided into four models namely station-rotation models, lab-rotataion models, flipped-classroom model, and individual-rotation models; (2) flex models; (3) self-blend models; and (4) enriched-virtual models. Clearly blended learning models of Innosight Institute can be shown in Figure 2.2. below this.

Figure 2. Models of Blended Learning

Rossett and Frazee (: 10-12) in a special report AMA blended learning models split into three, namely: (1) anchor blend, this model starts with defining events and real class, followed by a free experience that covers the interaction with online resources , learning activities in the workplace is structured, reference and online learning, recognition and assessment; (2) booked blend, a model which is characterized by the experience in three parts: an introduction, a learning experience that contains, real and important than instruski online or face to face and then something that expands and makes the learning into work practices. In other words, the model booked blend consists of planning and preparation online, actively training and face to face interaction, as well as the online application in the work; and (3) field blend, most models is different from the usual training. This model describes the employee-centered with each individual is surrounded by various types of assets and sustainable choices about when and where and whether to grab assets and that selection. Although classroom experiences are often part of a mixed field, it was just one of many methods, with a focus on continuous learning and reference and firm and free choice in employment. This model requires employees who are committed to continue the business and growth, relying on well-defined expectations, managers involved and assessments that point to resources. Key business according to this model is a treasure trove of resources and a few ways to find "what is" and "what is right" for you and those around you.

Seaman, and Garrett (2007: 5) Illustration Course Table of The prototypical classifications.

PROPORTION OF CONTENT DELIVERED ONLINE	TYPE OF COURSE	TYPICAL DESCRIPTION
0%	Traditional	Course with no online technology used —content is delivered in writing or orally.
1 to 29%	Web Facilitated	Course which uses web-based technology to facilitate what is essentially a face-to-face course. Uses a course management system (CMS) or web pages to post the syllabus and assignments, for example.
30 to 79%	Blended/Hybrid	Course that blends online and face-to-face delivery. Substantial proportion of the content is delivered online, typically uses online discussions, and typically has some face-toface meetings.
80 to 100%	Online	A course where most or all of the content is delivered online. Typically have no face-to-face meetings.

Based on some of the above description, it can be concluded notion Blended learning is a combination of face-based learning and online learning with online learning composition as much as 30-79%.

METHODS

The method used is descriptive research that "a method in researching the status of human groups, an object, a condition, a system of thought or a class of events in the present which aims to create a description, picture or painting in a systematic, factual and accurate about the facts, characteristics and relationships between phenomena investigated "(Nazir, 2005: 63). In this study the techniques used to collect data is a survey technique. According Singarimbun and Efendi (1996: 5), survey research is research taking sample from a population and using questionnaires as a data collection tool. The study population was all teachers bina bina are 31 teachers and all teachers are 19 teachers tutor Junior Open Kandanghaur officials, principals / vice-principals, and students Junior Open Kandanghaur as many as 315 students.

The sampling technique used in this study were selected on the basis of samples aiming (purposive sample) the sampling technique with consideration of specific purpose Arikunto, 2006: 130). The criteria of this sampling is class of experiments using ICT curriculum in the learning process, teachers bina science subjects and teachers responsible officials and the managers of class VIII Junior Open Kandanghaur. Therefore, the sample in this research is class VIII A with the overall number of students 34 students, two teachers and two teachers bina officials as well as a head of school / junior high school kepala Waki Open Kandanghaur-Indramayu. In conducting the necessary research methods and techniques as well as a means of collecting the relevant data. In this study the techniques used for data collection is done through: Spreading the questionnaire, Doing observation, and doing interviews.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Lesson Planning

Planning learning blended learning at Junior Open includes planning self-learning, face-to-face and online learning.

Figure 4.1 Diagram Results Blended Learning Teacher Resource Planning

From Figure 4.1 it appears that the blended learning plan the average teacher is already planning in accordance with a predetermined. In planning the independent study, there were 16.7% of teachers said always to plan, 50% said often, 33% said sometimes, and none that states rarely and never. In planning face to face, as much as 43.8% of teachers said always to plan, 50% said often, 6.3% said sometimes, and nothing that states rarely and never. But in planning online learning, as much as 12.5% of teachers said always to plan, 37.5% said often, 50% said sometimes, and nothing that states rarely and never.

In addition to the teachers, of the students also do research on them in the planning of the learning process. Students planning results shown in diagram 4.2 below:

Figure 4.2 Blended Learning By Students

From the results of planning research shows students learning blended learning, learning activities almost every self-learning, face-to-face and online learning, they do not do the planning primarily to-face activities, the majority of 52.9% of students said never. Thus virtually no questions of learning difficulties have been recorded and submitted prior to-face activities. Then when the independent study almost half the students claimed 47.1 occasionally perform planning at the time of self-learning, as well as online planning, 29.4% of students stated sometimes do the planning online.

2. Learning Implementation.

Implementation of blended learning, namely the implementation of self-learning, face-to-face and online learning. The data obtained from questionnaires distributed to students, teachers and teachers' community development officials. Here is the entirety of data:

Figure 3. Diagram Implementation of Blended Learning By Students

From Diagram 4.3 shows that the implementation of the blended learning by students shows most students still occasionally carry out online learning, independent study, and for the implementation of the face, most students rarely execute. Based on the diagram, on the implementation of the independent study, there were 8.5% of students stated always doing independent study, 10.6% stated often, 37.1% said sometimes, 26.2% said rarely, and 17.6% said never. Then in the implementation of the face carrying no students who declare always do face to face, 2.9% stated often, 25.5% said sometimes, 51% said rarely, and 20.6% said never. While in online learning implementation recorded 3.8% of students stating always doing online learning, 12.4% stated often, 38.8% said sometimes, 27.4% said rarely, and 17.6% said never.

While the results of the percentage of teachers in implementing the learning blended learning is as follows:

Diagram 4.4 implementation of blended learning that comes from teachers.

From Diagram 4.4 shows that the implementation of the overall learning belnded often are conducted by teachers. Based on the diagram, on the implementation of the independent study showed as many as 27% of teachers said

always doing independent study, 45% said often, 23% said sometimes, 5% said rarely, and none of the teachers who said never. On the implementation of face recorded 25% of teachers said always do face to face, 41.7% stated often, 33.3% said sometimes, and nothing that states rarely and never. On the implementation of online learning is recorded 27.3% of teachers stating always doing online learning, 36.4% stated often, 13.6% said sometimes, 13.6% said rarely, and 9.1% said never.

3. Evaluation of Learning.

Here is the result of the overall data on the evaluation of learning outcomes of the student, the teacher and the teacher tutor bina.

From Diagram 4.5 indicates that the frequency of students in carrying out the evaluation of learning outcomes, there were 19.2% of students stated always do the evaluation study, 15.5% stated often, 25.9% said sometimes, 17.6% said rarely, and 8% said never.

From the teacher tutors, the results of the evaluation study noted the majority of teachers tutor sometimes do, and no teacher can always make the evaluation study states. The diagram is based on a fraction of teachers 37.5% said often, and most of the 62.5% of teachers said sometimes, and nothing that states rarely and never.

While from the teacher coaching, the results of the evaluation study noted fraction 25% of teachers stating always make the evaluation of learning, and the remaining majority of 75% said often, and nothing is stated sometimes, rarely and never.

CONCLUSION

Planning often largely independent study conducted by the teacher tutors such as determining the subject matter topic, determining method / student learning. This greatly helps the students, so focused and directed in learning the subject matter, so that the self-learning process more effective. But unlike the teacher tutors, students do not perform as lesson planning palajaran determine the material to be studied in accordance with the purpose of learning. Media-related learning, teachers are generally only once officials determine media time for learning, it is most likely because the media in addition to the existing modules in TKB is not in accordance with the applicable curriculum and the media are not fit for use.

Lesson on self-learning activities of students using the media / learning resources in addition to modules such as textbooks, worksheets and Internet. When studying science subjects students sometimes use the media apart modul. Evaluasi study was conducted to determine the level of success of the learning process, the final test module is executed when the students complete study material / specific chapter. Based on the results of final test module is rarely implemented. But the final test units and test end of the semester students always carry it out.

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